

**GENERATIONAL DIFFERENCES IN USING SOCIAL MEDIA FOR
DESTINATION CHOICE****Ahmadbekova Farzinaxon Yusufbek qizi**

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Abstract. When it comes to making daily decisions, social media has changed people's lives and has become a vital source of information. The goal of this study and thesis is to see if there are any age differences in how people use social media and how it helps them in a destination choice. Only two generations were studied in this research: Generation Y and Baby Boomers. Social media is used as a marketing and tourism tool in today's world. In addition, the various generations and their relationships with social media are being researched as well. This article also includes the various marketing appeals and the relationship between them and cultural fascinations, as well as whether there is a generational difference in tourism commercial advertisements. The author created distinctive theories by finding answers to the research questions. An internet survey has been managed, where respondents have inquired about questions related to their social media usage, their goal choice, and final seen tourism advertisement. The survey included generally multiple-choice questions, with as it were a couple of open-ended questions. Measurable investigations have been conducted in arrange to test the theories and see whether there are noteworthy contrasts and in case presumptions were met. This result comes about demonstrated that the more seasoned tend to spend less time on social media, and share fewer individual photographs on it.

Keywords: social media, generational difference, destination choice, travel destination, internet, age difference, Generation Y, Baby boomers

Introduction

Due to the growth and value of the internet in our daily life, there opened new opportunities and changed the habits of people in the destination choosing process. Before the popularity of the internet, people used to choose places and destinations according to travel brochures or travel books.

Nowadays people used to choose travel destinations based on the results of online searching. Progressive development of the internet showed that making a destination choice for the younger generation is more comfortable via using social media platforms. However, for the older generation, this way is much more challenged. Millennials are well informed about modern technologies. Based on USG – user-generated content is known as feedback and reviews of previous users. In 2019 the number of users USG increased up to 59% (Macdonald, 2019). Since the users of social media and internet platforms increasing day by day, industries started to their use them for advertising. Different appeals mirror the culture`s values, so the advertising should be formed by the culture that is adopted. Different generations might use social media in a different manner that influences their choosing way of destination. The difference in age, gender, education, and level of internet use explains the diversity of the investigation process in travel information. The main emphasis that the author focused on was the difference between millennials and baby boomers. People who were born between 1981-1996 are called millennials. Millennials were born in a period when the internet started to change a society, which is why it was easy to accept new technologies for them. Nevertheless, baby boomers were born in a period of World War II, and because of it, they did not understand the new technologies (Smith, 2020). Therefore, they would rather to person-to-person contact than online communication.

Is there a difference between generations in using social media for a destination choice – it is a research question that is analyzed in this thesis. The results of the thesis should contribute a minimum of three approaches. First, exact consciousness of the importance of social media marketing in the tourism industry. Second, how using social media has become one of the important and huge destination-marketing tools. Third, understand the difference in destination choices between millennials and baby

boomers. Moreover, in the end, the research will concentrate on the appeals of advertisements.

Today the role of social media in tourism is so huge. With the development of searching platforms, people who are interested in creating touristic plans can find any informative details with all desires. As social media websites, the most popular ones are TripAdvisor, Booking.com and Trivago. According to studies, the social media is the best tool that used by tourists in their decision-making process. Therefore, as a main idea of the thesis, the author took into consideration the role of using social media in a destination choice of different generations. Especially, the difference between Millennials and baby boomers. In order to find answers to the questions given in the research, a method of analysis was chosen the online survey. Qualitative data results analyzed by using the Excel tool and investigated as a numerous method of analysis.

This article reviews a problem about the influence of social media in a decision process of a destination among generations. The solution and results of this article might be used in order to develop new market facilities in Uzbekistan. The main reason for research is to improve the tourist`s understanding of what criteria influence a destination choice. Does the generational difference in using social media affect the decision-making process of destination tourists? Does the type of social media platform influence a destination choice? These questions and more were taken as a problem statement.

Literature Review

2.1 Using social media in tourism

The usage of social media has increased dramatically in recent few years, having an impact not only on people`s daily lives but also on numerous industries, partially tourism and hospitality. Furthermore, social media started to play a crucial role in the business sector. It enables businesses to interact more directly with their customers and to engage regular customers with each other. Social media marketing is a method that creates content for various social media platforms to promote and engage people in a certain business(Schischlik, 2021). According to Khan and Jan (2015), social media marketing is the use of social media platforms to promote a brand, an organization, an

idea, or an event (Khan and Jan 2015). There are certain focal points to market via social media, but there are too related drawbacks as well. The key benefits of social media marketing are cost savings and increased reach of the company. Secondly, by adopting information for particular customers, a social media marketing agency can establish interactions that allow customers to develop products and services that match their specific needs. Nevertheless, the online environment makes not only advantages but also some challenges and issues for the process of social media marketing.

The role of engagement in social media is enormous. That is why social media marketing allows businesses to communicate with their customers as a result of the input they receive. In promoting a product, it is essential to take into account the time of posting, what kind of message will be and what will be used as a title of the post. Creativity and good strategy require important parts in this case. Storytelling will be an ideal option. It helps to attract and interest more customers to willing to purchase the products (Dukart, 2018). It is fact that it had been a big influence on social media on marketing in the tourism industry. The first thought of anybody before a trip is choosing a travel destination. Even in the past while people used to organize trips using the help of travel agents. Therefore, they were responsible for every detail, due to others had no connection with needed resources. There is a huge difference between the 1980s travelling from now. The main purpose of mobile phones was communication and not more and photos had taken with special carefulness. Nowadays social media opens new horizons of priorities in the tourism industry such as sharing photos and videos of destinations, reviews, feedback, and experiences those other tourists can use as recommendations before their travel.

2.2 Role of social media as a tool of destination

The important thing is the difference between social media and a media of conversation. Social media is a collection of websites and a tool that helps people with sharing content materials quickly. Social media has many reasons for usage and the most common cause is as an internet platform and showing some moments of life. Additional usage of this tool might be online discussions, shopping, anonym forums, customer reviews, and some rating systems as well. The ability of businesses shares a

different kind of content through videos, pictures, words, or audio is named conversational media. It is called conversation marketing too. This conception gives to employees to see the various potential types of communication between their brand and consumers. These days, travel business markets started to use digital devices in their marketing strategies, because of high competition in a destination. As World Tourism Organization (WTO) published over the last decade, the desire to have planned management in a destination of tourism rapidly increased. Destination Management Organizations allow seeing and analyzing the new updated information about a particular destination and its attractiveness. Especially, for leisure tourists, it is important to have some research about hotels, restaurants, upcoming events and festivals, prices, and reviews of the destination. Based on the target and budget of the organization will be determined plan of action. One of the main goals of the destination management organizations has to create a community that is interested in a touristic destination. The simple way of this process is to collect the content of users, because a tourist can find photos and videos, reviews and comments that previous visitors are left. A most important reason for using a destination management organization is the availability of online surveys, questionnaires, and reviews about destinations. An important event in recent years was the development of social media that allows users to create and share content such as blogs, and vlogs. This kind of benefit helps to create a good relationship with consumers, so in the end, they become closer. Due to this every airline and hotel needs to have a strong marketing strategy to have a demand for tourists globally. Hays has recommended a special strategic cycle that helps to have great social media marketing. A cycle includes five steps. Firstly, the company should catch up with new users for participation and then keep followed ones and this is how loyalty will be built. Hence, after this process company should give current personalized information to their consumers. And the final step, the company can start to attract its customers.

According to it:

Q1 Millennials are more attached to searching online reviews, before choosing destinations rather than baby boomers.

2.3 Using of social media in a different generation

The presence of a difference between generations is important for the marketing context. Because it helps to build a good relationship and enhance trust. People who were born from 1946-to 1964 years called the "Baby boomers". They think that social media and new developing technology may destroy and change their typical style of life (Marzullo, 2019). Afterwards came "Generation X" a group of people who were born from 1965 to the 1980s. They did not have an access to the internet during their childhood period. The next generation is "Gen Y" also called "Millennials" who were born from 1981 to 1995. Changing the near future is the main goal of this generation. Finally, "Gen Z" from 1996 – 2012, "Zoomers" who has been raised with the internet (Marzullo, 2019). In addition, the last children of the world are YouTube and iPhones "Generation Alphas" from 2013 until nowadays. The most internet-savvy generation.

№	Generation	Born year ranges	Current age
1.	Baby boomers	1946-1964	57-75
2.	Generation X	1965-1980	41-56
3.	Generation Y/Millennials	1981-1995	27-40
4.	Generation Z	1996-2012	2-26
5.	Generation Alpha	2013-until now	

Table 1. Overview of Generations

Source: Adapted from Marzullo, D. 2019, own creation

According to statistics by the Statista website (Figure 1) show, an overview of the age range of internet users for 2022 is presented. 99% of users are 18-19-year-old. 98% are in the age group of people between 30-49 years. 96% of users are people of 50-64-years. Moreover, there are 75% of 65+ years old users actively use the internet in the

United States (Statista, 2021). For analyses, of the difference in using social media between generations the author focused more on Gen Y and baby boomers.

Figure 1. The percentage of using the internet by the age group in the United States in 2021 (Statista, 2021).

Due to a lack of using the internet regularly and considering the age of the generation of baby boomers, the usage of social media is better for Millennials. Gen Y had a positive idea of the importance of the internet from their childhood. Accordingly, to survey of the respondents of different ages in the USA that was organized in 2019, concluded that millennials use the internet more than baby boomers. Therefore, based on these details the questions given below had been created:

Q2: Internet using skills of Millennials are more progressive than baby boomers

Q3: The activity of Millennials on social media is higher than baby boomers

Q4: Spending time of Millennials on social media is longer than baby boomers

Q5: Millennials share more photos and videos on social media than baby boomers

Q6: Millennials share their own experience on social media more than baby boomers

On a general basis generation of Millennials share photos and videos, of their personal experience on social media platforms while baby boomers in most cases use smartphones for mobile communication, taking pictures or sending messages, and photos to family members and friends. All generation may understand the usage of social media and its culture in a different manner. This specific difference helps to compare generations' contrast in a practice. It means that generation has a big influence

on the popularity of applications or types of media fields. Moreover, the survey that was conducted in 2015 approved that there are essential differences in media usage between baby boomers and millennials (Bowe and Wohn, 2015).

Methodology

Design of research is a structure that consists of different methods, techniques, and approaches that are used to analyze, gather and define data. There are two types of research design: quantitative and qualitative. Qualitative research concerns the numbers, tables, and graphs, which are managed by collecting data to create the main hypotheses and concepts. Quantitative research in its turn might be used by organizing surveys, making experiments, or doing some analysis. Making interviews, focus groups, ethnography differences, and literature reviews are the different ways of collecting data for qualitative research. Therefore, for this article as research design selected conducting an e-survey. In fact, there are pros and cons of online surveys. It is really easy and appropriate to conduct an online survey. The first advantage of an online survey is access to any comfortable leisure time for respondents. Secondly, it is the way to conduct data in a short period. For the reason that the process is without an interviewer, the respondents have the availability of being freer and without any doubt answer the questions.

By using social media platforms, the author chose the best way to distribute the survey. It was easy, fast, and convenient. The online survey matured by using Google Forms. The author`s page on Instagram (via posting story and linking in the bio), personal channel on Telegram, and "Uzsport_no1" page on Instagram served as a distribution tool to share the questionnaire form. In order to collect a wide range of ages the questions were made in the Uzbek language as well. The link was activated on March 21, 2022 at 11:46 pm. By sharing the link of the survey over the Telegram, the level of attachment of students was rapidly high in a few minutes. To reach enough audience of the students (mainly Gen Z) people between 15-26 years was easy. The survey was available for 8 days – until March 29, 2022. Access to the survey was closed due to limitations on the number of respondents of Gen Z. Excepting the age,

nationality, and level of education the respondent has a further question about his name. It shows that the respondents are real.

The published story posts on Instagram of the author`s account be located in Appendix 6.1, the story of the "Uzsport_no1" page on Instagram in Appendix 6.2, and the shared posts on Telegram in Appendix 6.3. Overall, there were 300 valid responses gathered in the given period. In order to end up the survey, all 15 questions had to be answered. Therefore, all questions were fully answered by respondents. After enough data is gathered, the result will be evaluated by using Excel or Google Forms tool so that the author can do some statistical analysis using charts, diagrams, and tables. It is helpful to compare the hypotheses, which are defined in the literature review part.

The goal of this investigation is to identify the influence of generation on a destination choice through using social media. The Google Forms tool is used for a reason. Firstly, it had the privilege to save automatically the results of the survey as a file in Excel. It provides the creation of pie charts, bar charts, and graphs in an easy way. Question 15 was the last open-ended. This refers to one advantage side of using social media.

Analysis and Results

Data Analysis

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Figure 1. Internet using skills of respondents

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According to survey results, the respondents varied from the age of 7-75 years.

Generations	Count	%
Generation Z	240	80%
Generation Y	39	13%
Generation X	14	4.7%
Baby boomers	7	2.3%

Table 2. Participation of different generations in the survey

Respondents are grouped into the generation. Overall, there were 240 respondents the Generation Z (80%), 39 people were part of Millennials (13%), 14 people for Generation X (4.7%) and finally, 7 respondents were baby boomers (2.3%).

This section shows a descriptive analytics overview and the difference between the age and other particular sections. In order to investigate the results of the survey. Question 1 refers to the difference in using the internet between two generations: Millennials and Baby boomers. It should be examined therefore in the survey the author asked about skills in using the internet.

The total number of Millennials consists of 39 respondents between the ages of 27-40 years. 18 out of it classify themselves as a very good user of the internet, 15 respondents with a good level of use, and 6 who use it at a fair level. Nobody picked the option “Poor” or “Very poor” user of the internet. Consequently, the total number of participants of generation baby boomers were only 10. Regarding four of them are Good level, 1 Fair, 1 Very Poor and only one was a Very good use of the internet. It shows that Generation Y (Millennials) are more experienced and advanced in using the internet than baby boomers. Question 1 is proved (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Analytics of the internet using skills of the respondents

One of the important factors in a destination choice might be online reviews and shared experiences of other visitors. To identify the most popular reason for choosing the destination there was a question about the last visited destination as an experience of participant.

Almost half of the respondents 53% trust their family, friends, and relatives. 20.3% of respondents by watching videos on YouTube, 15% by posts and

recommendations of bloggers, 7.3% by reading travel books, and only 4.3% after watching film/TV series.

Conclusion

Survey results indicate that Millennials are a more tech-savvy generation than baby boomers. It means nowadays, social media marketers may attract more people from Gen Y. Especially, the influence of Instagram and TikTok in a destination choice is rapidly growing. Bloggers, marketers and other influencers may use this opportunity in their business projects. In addition, the findings of article might recommend in the future studies of the following using sections:

- Expanding the target market of tour agencies
- As an education source for students/researchers
- In report and analytics searching
- As an additional source

Certainly, as expected, in the process of organizing this article, there were some limitations. Firstly, it is a little size of sample data. Secondly, difficult to find enough respondents for each generation group. Especially, it was a challenge to find enough number of baby boomers. Considering these factors will encourage having another extra research with this topic of article: generational differences in using social media as a destination choice. The goal of this article was to learn the main differences between generations and their use of social media in a destination choice. Another idea of article was what kind of social media is much more popular between two chosen generations. In order to have a total overview of all topics learned an online survey was conducted.

According to survey results, the most popular social media in a territory of Tashkent turned up Telegram. This type of messenger is trouble-free to understand and to start use for millennials rather than other social media. Baby boomers use Telegram in a daily life as well. Results of an online survey show that Millennials advanced users of social media than baby boomers. For that, reason Gen Y agree with fact that they choose the travel destination by analyzing reviews of other tourists via online searching. When it comes to baby boomers, they prefer to consult their trip planning

with professionals or by advices of family members. Moreover, the main purpose of travelling for baby boomers is visiting their family members; however, baby boomers travel for leisure. Especially nowadays, Gen Z trusts internet research feedback. Online review, rating system results influence on people is so high. Rapid growth of popularity social media plays a huge role on it. There were six hypotheses. They are proved according to the results of the survey. It became known that Millennial`s skill of usage internet is more progressive. Furthermore, activeness of millennials is differed pretty strongly than baby boomers. Gen Y is already ready to be open to the world and share their own photos, videos, and experiences on the social media. In the general, the survey gave all expected details and was helpful during preparing analytics of an article. However, in order to get more detailed answers and results there is a clear need for supplementary research.

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